

A New Reagent System for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Selenium in Environmental and Cosmetic Samples

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Manuscript received 3 July 1997, accepted 1 August 1997

A new reagent system using leuco crystal violet (LCV) for the determination of selenium is described. The method is based on the reaction of selenium with acidified potassium iodide to liberate iodine which oxidizes LCV to form crystal violet having absorption maxima at 593 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0.5–4.5 μg of Se in a final solution volume of 25 ml (0.02–0.18 ppm). The apparent molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $3.68 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0002 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The method has been satisfactorily applied to the determination of selenium in a variety of environmental and cosmetic samples at ppm level. The method is highly sensitive, selective and convenient. Tellurium which interferes in most of the other methods does not interfere in this method.

Selenium(IV) is a paradoxical element reported to have a double character well known as an essential as well as toxic trace element¹. Selenium is a by-product of certain industrial and agricultural processes and there are cases where selenium from such sources has caused environmental damage². It is widely used in industries as an additive to dyes, lubricants, plastics and rubber². In China selenium deficiency in soil is associated with Keshan disease and Kaschin-Beck disease^{3,4}. It's efficiency causes pulmonary oedema, abdominal pain, jaundice, chronic gastrointestinal diseases, hair loss and fatigue in human beings. In recent years some increase in the selenium level in human hair has been found¹. It also plays a major role in plants (cruciferae family) life-cycle and can be found in concentration as high as 1.5%⁵. The TLV value for selenium compounds in air² is 0.1–0.2 mg dm^{-3} and in water is 4 ppm⁶.

Several analytical methods are available that can measure selenium quantitatively in ppm or submicrogram levels^{7–11}. Various spectrophotometric methods using reagents 3,3-diaminobenzidine¹², dithiozone, *o*-phenylenediamine¹³, 8-hydroxyquinoline¹⁴, 2,3-diamino-1,4-dibromonaphthalene¹⁵, J-acid^{16,17} etc. have been reported in the literature for the determination of traces of selenium in various environmental samples.

Here, a simple, sensitive and selective method using a new reagent leuco crystal violet (LCV) has been reported for the determination of selenium in various samples. The proposed method is based on the liberation of iodine by the reaction of selenium with potassium iodide in acidic medium. The liberated iodine selectively oxidizes leuco crystal violet, and the crystal violet dye so formed shows maximum absorbance at 593 nm. This method has a sensitivity of 0.02 ppm of selenium (Beer's law range 0.02–0.18 ppm). The method has been successfully applied for the determination of selenium in wide variety of environmental and cosmetic samples.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the crystal violet dye showed

maximum absorbance at 593 nm. Reagent blank showed negligible absorbance at this wavelength. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 0.5–4.5 μg of selenium per 25 ml of the final solution (0.02–0.18 ppm) at 593 nm. The apparent molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $3.68 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0002 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. Repeatability of the method was checked by the replicate analysis of the working standard solution containing 3 μg per 25 ml of selenium over a period of seven days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.015 and 2.92% respectively.

Constant and maximum absorbance values were obtained when 1 ml of 0.5% KI, 2 ml of 2 M HCl, 1 ml of LCV and ~2 ml of 2M NaOH were used. The most suitable temperature for full color development was found in the range 40–50°. Once developed, the colour was found to be stable for several days under the proposed experimental conditions. Constant absorbance values were obtained in the pH range 5.5–6.7. Increase of pH above 6.7 severely affected the stability of the dye. Color development did not take place below pH 5.5. 20–25 min time was necessary for the complete color development.

The validity of the method was assessed by investigating the effect of foreign species and other common ions in the analysis of selenium. The tolerance limit value (ppm) of different foreign species in a solution containing 3.0 $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$ of selenium were found to be : Ag^I, K⁺, Ba^{II} (4500); Ca^{II} (4000); Te^{IV}, sulphate, phosphate (2500); Pb^{II}, Sn^{IV} (1500); Co^{II}, Cd^{II}, Fe^{III} (1200); Cr^{III}, Al^{III}, Zn^{II}, Be^{II} (850); As^V, Bi^{III} (800). Hg^{II} and Mn^{IV} had a positive catalyzing effect on the color reaction. Cu^{II}, Fe^{II} and Sn^{II} which are most common interferents were found not to interfere upto 80 ppm, if masked with EDTA.

Experimental

A Systronics 108 spectrophotometer, a Systronics 331 pH meter, a Pimco calibrated rotameter and 35 ml midjet impingers (for air sampling) were used.

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade or the best

quality available. Double-distilled deionised water was used throughout.

A 1 mg ml⁻¹ stock solution of selenium was prepared by dissolving selenium (100 mg) in concentrated nitric acid (5 ml) by gentle heating and evaporating to dryness. The dried mass was then dissolved in distilled water (100 ml) and a working standard solution was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution¹⁶. Aqueous solutions of 0.5% KI, 2 M HCl and 2 M NaOH were prepared. Solution of leuco crystal violet (Eastman Kodak) (250 g) was prepared in a mixture of phosphoric acid (3 ml) and water (200 ml) and then diluted to 1 dm³ with water. Aqueous 5% HNO₃ was used as absorbing solution.

Calibration curve : To an aliquot of a working standard solution containing 0.5–4.5 µg of selenium was added KI solution (1 ml) followed by HCl (2 ml). The mixture was shaken gently till the appearance of yellow color, indicating the liberation of iodine. Then LCV solution (1 ml) was added to it and shaken for 2 min, followed by addition of 2 M NaOH (~2 ml). The solution was kept in a thermostat (45°) for ~2 min, the volume made up to 25 ml by adding deionized water and set aside for ~25 min for full color development. The absorbance of the crystal violet dye obtained was then measured at 593 nm against the reagent blank.

Selenium in water : An aliquot (5 ml) of polluted water sample was taken and selenium was determined by the proposed and reported¹⁶ methods (Table 1). To further check the applicability and recovery of the proposed method, known amounts of selenium was added to water and Se determined by the proposed method with excellent recoveries (≥ 98.01 ± 0.08), in agreement with the reported method.

Selenium in plant materials : The sample of plant material (5 g) was digested with HNO₃ (10 ml) for 20 min. After cooling, perchloric acid (0.5 ml) was added and heating was continued for another 10 min until the evaluation of ample fumes of perchloric acid. Water (10 ml) was added to the cooled residue and heated again for 10 min. Then HCl (5 ml) was added and heating continued for 10 min to convert Se^{VI} to Se^{IV}¹⁸. The contents were diluted to 50 ml after adding EDTA solution (10 ml). Aliquot of this solution (5 ml) was taken and Se determined as described above (Table 1).

Selenium in cigarette smoke : Selenium is present in cigarette smoke¹⁹. Different brands of cigarettes with known mass (2 g) were analyzed for the determination of selenium in smoke. The smoke was drawn through absorbing solution (10 ml) contained in two midjet impingers connected in series to a source of suction at a flow rate of 200 ml min⁻¹. After sampling, aliquot (5 ml) of the sample solution was analyzed as described above (Table 1).

Selenium in steel plant dust : Various steel dust samples were collected from high volume sampler at the flow rate of 200 ml min⁻¹ from different sites of the nearby steel plant. The samples (27.0 mg) was digested with acid mix-

TABLE I—APPLICATION OF THE METHOD FOR DETERMINATION OF SELENIUM IN DIFFERENT SAMPLES* BY THE PRESENT AND REPORTED METHOD

Sample volume or mass**	Se originally found (µg)	Se added (µg)	Total Se found (µg)	% Recovery
Natural water ^a	—	2.00	1.96 (1.94)	98.00 (97.00)
	—	3.00	2.95 (2.92)	98.30 (97.33)
	—	4.00	3.90 (3.93)	97.75 (98.25)
	2.48 (2.51)	1.00	3.45 (3.48)	97.00 (97.00)
Polluted water ^b	2.90 (2.89)	1.00	3.87 (3.85)	97.00 (96.41)
	3.18 (3.16)	1.00	4.16 (4.12)	98.00 (96.50)
	1.23 (1.18)	1.00	2.19 (2.13)	96.00 (95.00)
	1.51 (1.45)	1.00	2.48 (2.39)	97.00 (94.00)
Plant materials ^c	2.23 (2.16)	1.00	3.19 (3.16)	96.00 (95.00)
	4.21 (4.12)	—	—	—
Cruciferae plant	3.70 (3.60)	—	—	—
	—	2.00	1.96 (1.92)	98.16 (96.00)
Steel plant dust ^d	—	3.00	2.92 (2.95)	97.30 (98.33)
	—	4.00	3.93 (3.85)	98.25 (96.25)
	1.26 (1.18)	2.00	3.21 (3.10)	97.50 (96.00)
S ₂	1.08 (1.00)	2.00	3.06 (2.94)	99.00 (97.50)
	0.46 (0.39)	3.00	3.33 (3.31)	95.66 (94.00)
Cigarette smoke ^e	1.16 (1.13)	3.00	4.07 (4.01)	97.00 (96.00)
	1.10 (1.07)	3.00	4.01 (3.91)	97.00 (94.66)
	1.30 (1.28)	2.00	3.26 (3.20)	98.00 (96.00)
Hair sample ^f	1.55 (1.35)	2.00	3.48 (3.26)	96.50 (95.50)
	0.98 (0.96)	2.00	2.92 (2.84)	97.00 (94.00)
Lipstick ^g	0.94 (0.91)	2.00	2.87 (2.78)	96.50 (93.50)
	1.30 (1.26)	2.00	3.22 (3.10)	96.00 (92.00)
L ₃	1.18 (1.15)	2.00	3.14 (3.10)	98.00 (97.50)
	0.78 (0.72)	2.00	2.72 (2.62)	97.00 (95.00)

* Figures in parentheses are those by reported method (Ref. 16).

** 5 ml aliquot of sample solution; a, b = 100 ml, c = 5 g, d = 27 mg, e = 2 g, f = 0.1 g, g = 0.5 g.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON WITH OTHER SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHODS

Reagent	Medium/pH	λ_{\max} nm	Beer's law range, mg dm^{-3}	Remarks
3,3'-Diamino-benzidine ^a	Aqueous	420	0.1–10	Colored salts oxidants Bi^{III} , Cr^{II} , Mo^{IV} , V^{V} etc. interfere
2,3-Diamino-naphthalene ^b	Acidic 2.0(\pm 0.03)	378.5	0.5–12	Less sensitive and most of oxidants and reductants interfere
O. Phenylenc-diamine ^c	Toluene 1.5–2.5	335	upto 4	1–3 h for reaction Fe^{III} , Bi^{II} interfere
4-Nitrophenyl - hydrazine-8-quinolinol ^d	Aqueous 9–11	550	0.28–1.8	Fe^{IV} , Cu^{II} , V^{V} interfere
6 Amino-1-naphthol-3-sulphonic acid ^e	Aqueous 1–2.5	392	0.08–0.8	Non- extractive and less sensitive
J-acid Extraction ^f	Butanol 1.5–6.2	520	0.03–0.3	Extractive and less sensitive
LCV ^g	Acidic 5.5–6.7	593	0.02–0.18	Non-expactive simple and selective

^aRef. 12, ^bRef. 21, ^cRef. 22, ^dRef. 23, ^eRef 16, ^fRef. 17, ^gPresent method.

ture and then evaporated to 2 ml. The contents were cooled and boiled with HCl (10 ml) for 10 min. Again contents were cooled and diluted to 25 ml with water. Aliquot (5 ml) was taken and analyzed for selenium as recommended above (Table 1).

Selenium in human hair : Human hair sample (0.1 g) was digested with acid mixture (HCl : HNO_3 , 3 : 2 v/v; 10 ml) for 10 min. The contents were then cooled and made alkaline with 10% NaOH (pH ~9.0), and analyzed as above (Table 1).

Selenium in cosmetic sample (lipstick) : Selenium is reported to be present in various cosmetic samples²⁰. Samples (0.5 g) of several brands of lipstick were dissolved in alcohol to extract the organic material contained in lipsticks. The residue was gently heated with conc. nitric acid (10 ml) for 10 min and the contents were cooled and boiled with HCl (10 ml) for 10 min to convert Se^{VI} to Se^{IV} . Sample residue was cooled and diluted to 50 ml with water. The aliquot (5 ml) was analyzed by the above method as well as by reported method¹⁰ (Table 1).

Application : The above results (Tables 1) are in good agreement with those obtained by the J-acid method (R)¹⁶.

The proposed method has been compared with other spectrophotometric methods and found to be more sensitive and selective (Table 2). This method is a good alternative of some of the reported methods. The advantage of the proposed method is mainly due to its sensitivity, simplicity, selectivity and higher stability of the color solution.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur, for facilities.

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